

Supplementary Materials for:

Extreme mismatch between phytoplankton and grazers during Arctic spring blooms and consequences for the pelagic food-web

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Supplementary materials

1 Water masses - presence and abundance

Water mass definitions used here follow those developed by Sundfjord et al., 2020 (<https://doi.org/10.7557/nlrs.5707>). In May 2021 two distinct water masses were encountered on the CTD section (Figure S1a). Polar Water (PW) to the north and warm Polar Water to the south. Further south still, Atlantic water (AW) was encountered in a single CTD station taken at 73.6° N. The very straight lines in TS-space between PW and AW indicate that wPW was likely a mixing product of these two end members. The drawing upwards of data points towards the Gade line in the data within the PW polygon indicates the clear influence of melting sea ice towards the surface of the more northerly stations. Note that the Gade line (blue line figure S1) and run-off mixing line (red line, figure S1) are given arbitrary starting points. These two mixing lines are included to show the gradient of these lines to aid interpretation, not as particular mixing lines for any observed water parcels.

In May 2022 the water mass structure was broadly comparable to May 2021 (Figure S1b). Most data points fall into the PW and wPW classes. In 2022 no 'pure' AW was detected, but in May 2021, AW was only encountered much further south than southern end of the CTD section. This was likely also the case in 2022, and it is also highly likely the wPW seen in 2021 is a product of unobserved AW further south/west mixing with PW, given the trajectory of the data in TS space from PW through the wPW towards the AW end-member region. At ~76.5° N the data fall closely parallel to a Gade line, indication the very strong influence of sea ice melt around that part of the transect.

As noted by Sundfjord et al., (2020) wPW can consist of "a) PW that has been heated through solar radiation or b) a mixing product between AW/mAW and PW, the latter often being found in the (seasonal) halocline." In the water mass fraction analysis that follows, to exclude the possible influence of insolation on the temperature or salinity (through ice melting), data from shallower than 20 m are omitted. Further, we note that the wPW data cloud in TS-space in both 2021 and 2022 inclines upward towards AW rather than mAW (modified Atlantic Water). For all observed T and S data points the fractional composition of two end-member water masses, PW ($T = -1^{\circ} \text{C}$, $S = 34.62$) and AW ($T = 3.5^{\circ} \text{C}$, $S = 35.2$) are calculated. The numerical solution for the two fractions uses a least-squares procedure (matlab "lsqin" function), with conditions applied in the solver such that each evaluated fraction must have a value lying between zero and one, and that the sum of the fractions must equal one. The results are shown as F_{AW} (the fraction of Atlantic Water on each CTD section) and, by definition, the fraction of PW, $F_{PW} = (1 - F_{AW})$.

Supplementary Figure S1. a) (left panel) TS diagram from CTD stations taken in May 2021, shown in figure 1. Data are coloured by station latitude; water mass types show as filled polygons are defined in the text. Lines are freezing point (dashed), run-off (red) and Gade lines (blue). b) (right panel) as for a) but May 2022.

In May 2021 the fractional analysis (Figure S2) follows closely the temperature structure (Figure 2, main text). $F_{AW} = 0$ corresponds to the sub-zero PW north of the front. In both years there is a weak vertical front around $F_{AW} = 0.5$ with the much stronger sloping front around $F_{AW} = 0.2$. Both years also exhibit the presence of a sub-surface patch of more AW-influence water beneath more clearly defined PW north of the location of the surface front. In May 2021 the highest values of $F_{AW} = 0.65$ were found shallower than 150 m and south of 76.5° N. In May 2022 the section extended further south, with $F_{AW} = 0.80$ in the upper 200 m and south of 75.8° N.

Supplementary Figure S2. FAW, the fraction of Atlantic Water within CTD section on 30° N May 2021. Contour interval 0.05. Open circles denoted CTD station locations. Fraction of PW, $FPW = (1 - FAW)$, see text for details.

Supplementary Figure S3. As for Figure S2 but for May 2022.

Supplementary Figure S4. Magnitude of sea-surface temperature (SST) gradient, SST, and sea-ice concentration (%) in 2021 (a, b, c, respectively) and in 2022 (d, e, f, respectively). Depth contours in a and d in white represent the 200 and 300 m isobaths. Main station locations indicated with red circles. Cyan line in a and d represent the 0% sea-ice cover contour.

Supplementary Figure S5. A) Example of a thirty-minute portion of the clean echosounder data on 20 May

Supplementary Table T1: Depths at which each gear sampled for the different parameters estimated at main sampling stations. Date sampled, position, and bottom depth for each station are presented in Table 1 (main text).

Gear	Niskin bottle	Multinet	Tucker Trawl	Pelagic Trawl
Parameter	Chl a concentration	Mesozooplankton	Macrozooplankton	Fish
M21_S1	5,10,20,50,100,192	180-100-50-20-0	160	160
M21_S2	5,10,20,50,185	100-50-20-0	120	160
M21_S3	5,10,20,50,100,231	218-200-100-50-20-0		
M21_S3*			120	120
M21_S4	5,10,20,50,10,248	230-200-100-50-20-0	120	100
M21_S5	10,20,50,75,100,297	300-200-100-50-20-0		80
M21_S6	5,10,20,50,100	340-200-100-50-20-0	30	173
M22_S1	5,10,25,50,100,190	178-100-50-20-0	25	
M22_S2	5,10,25,50,100,210	200-150-100-50-20-0	180	
M22_S2*				180
M22_S3	5,10,20,50,100,346	262-200-100-50-20-0		
M22_S3*			115, 230	118, 200
M22_S3.5		340-0 (WP2)		
M22_S4	5,10,20,50,100,341	335-200-100-50-20-0	60, 120	60, 100
M22_S4.5		290-0 (WP2)		
M22_S5	5,10,20,50,100,360	352-200-100-50-20-0	140, 250	55, 140
M22_S6	5,10,25,50,100,270	342-200-100-50-20-0	250	70, 140

Supplementary Table T2: Fish school detection parameters used in the analysis of the shipboard EK60 echosounder.

<i>Parameter</i>	<i>Value</i>
Echogram Threshold (dB)	-65.00
Capelin average target strength (dB)	-55.15
Average weight of capelin caught (g)	4.60
Minimum total school height (m)	10.00
Minimum candidate length (m)	5.00
Minimum candidate height (m)	2.00
Maximum vertical linking distance (m)	5.00
Maximum horizontal linking distance (m)	20.00
Minimum total school length (m)	40.00

Supplementary Table T3: Sailbuoy EK80 parameters and calibration details. during autonomous surveys in 2021 and 2022.

Platform	Transducer	Frequency range (kHz)	Power (W)	Pulse length (ms)	Pulse repetition (Hz)	Calibration (date / sphere size (mm))
Iskant 2021	ES200-7CDK	185-255	150	1024	0.5	2021-04-28/ 38.1
Iskant 2022	ES200-7CDK	200	75	1024	0.5	No calibration

Supplementary Table T4. Abundance and Biomass of main mesozooplankton groups at all stations sampled with Multinet (180µm) in May 2021 and May 2022.

	Calanus spp.	other large copepods	small copepods	Meroplankton	copepod nauplii	other taxa	Total
Abundance (ind. m⁻²)							
M21_S1	6045	124	70968	1808	20040	6817	105802
M21_S2	3498	18	31680	1188	9179	10833	56396
M21_S3	8108	16	29243	3902	23491	26003	90763
M21_S4	9780	129	34247	5092	14830	38047	102125
M21_S5	8088	309	46215	13221	67455	30804	166092
M21_S6	179585	857	115104	43731	290802	297097	927174
Mean 2021*	7104	119	42471	5042	26999	22501	104235
Biomass (mg DM m⁻²)							
M21_S1	755	63	408	2	90	66	1385
M21_S2	689	0	155	1	41	55	942
M21_S3	624	26	129	4	106	400	1288
M21_S4	801	16	136	5	67	198	1223
M21_S5	501	95	137	13	304	190	1241
M21_S6	2211	288	310	44	1309	574	4736
mean 2021*	674	40	193	5	121	182	1216
M22_S1	1214	0	571	1	167	298	2251
M22_S2	458	4	369	13	160	541	1545
M22_S3	671	42	244	1	119	5380	6457
M22_S3.5	861	103	131	26	66	117	1303
M22_S4	286	58	193	54	100	252	943
M22_S4.5	480	32	199	28	78	70	889
M22_S5	938	29	211	95	171	192	1637
M22_S6	698	79	217	49	138	146	1327
Mean 2022	701	43	267	33	125	875	2044

*mean excludes MS21_S6

Supplementary Table T5: Abundance and Biomass of main taxonomic groups at all stations sampled with the Tucker Trawl in May 2021 and May 2022. nd= not determined

Station	Sample depth (m)	Euphausiids	Amphipods	Chaetognaths	Pteropods	Gelatinous taxa	Copepods & other	Total
		Abundance (ind m ⁻³)						
M21_S1	160	0.024	0.027	0.063	0.010	0.005	nd	0.129
M21_S2	120	0.039	0.038	0.450	0.003	0.005	nd	0.536
M21_S3	80	0.087	0.000	0.319	0.004	0.011	nd	0.421
M21_S4	120	0.277	0.009	0.161	0.005	0.029	nd	0.480
M21_S6	30						nd	
M22_S5	140	0.009	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	nd	0.009
M22_S5	250	0.116	0.000	0.089	0.000	0.000	nd	0.205
M22_S3	115	0.143	0.000	0.182	0.001	0.001	nd	0.327
M22_S3	230	0.128	0.000	0.276	0.001	0.006	nd	0.410
M22_S4	60	0.000	0.000	0.096	0.000	0.000	nd	0.096
M22_S4	120	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.006	0.000	nd	0.006
M22_S6	250	0.114	0.000	1.753	0.000	0.029	nd	1.896
M22_S1	25	0.070	0.034	0.007	0.012	0.005	nd	0.127
M22_S2	180	0.245	0.023	0.461	0.002	0.050	nd	0.781
Biomass (mg DM m⁻³)								
M21_S1	160	0.083	0.009	0.359	0.124	0.252	0.858	1.684
M21_S2	120	0.194	0.021	1.565	0.053	0.035	1.862	3.729
M21_S3	80	0.279	0.000	0.987	0.140	0.174	1.937	3.517
M21_S4	120	0.994	4.410	0.521	0.052	1.352	0.000	7.328
M21_S6	30	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.045	0.045
M22_S5	140	0.049	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.102	0.151
M22_S5	250	0.749	0.000	0.769	0.000	0.000	1.798	3.316
M22_S3	115	0.517	0.000	0.786	0.047	0.000	2.446	3.796
M22_S3	230	0.851	0.000	1.552	0.008	0.309	2.182	4.902
M22_S4	60	0.000	0.000	0.181	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.181
M22_S4	120	0.000	0.000	0.000	0.080	0.000	0.000	0.080
M22_S6	250	0.462	0.000	3.199	0.000	2.820	1.267	7.749
M22_S1	25	0.249	0.128	0.000	0.151	1.147	8.848	10.524
M22_S2	180	1.096	2.537	0.867	2.537	0.796	2.537	10.369

Supplementary Table T6: Capelin school density (and standard deviation), school biomass, and school height of fish schools detected by the shipboard EK60 echosounder. Regional division was based on the approximate position of the surface front in each year. In 2021 The North region included schools of capelin found above 76.75° N and the South region included schools of capelin found below 76.75° N. In 2022 The North region included schools of capelin found above 75.9° N and the South region included schools of capelin found below 75.9° N.

<i>Year</i>	<i>Region</i>	<i>Mean School Volumetric Density (standard deviation)</i> <i>(fish/m³)</i>	<i>Mean School Volumetric biomass (standard deviation)</i> <i>(g/m³)</i>	<i>Mean School Height (standard deviation)</i> <i>(m)</i>
2021	North	0.13 (0.12)	0.68 (0.57)	13.02 (10.5)
	South	0.68 (0.41)	3.19 (1.93)	6.80 (3.11)
	All	0.63 (0.42)	2.18 (1.99)	7.31 (4.54)
2022	North	0.31 (0.28)	1.35 (1.20)	14.09 (9.5)
	South	0.56 (0.41)	2.44 (1.76)	5.33 (3.56)
	All	0.52 (0.40)	2.25 (1.73)	6.88 (6.07)